

IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF FINANCIAL INDICATORS IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Increasing the financial indicators of the enterprises is of great importance in modernizing various sectors of the country's economy and increasing the resistance of the products created in the national economy of the country to market competition. Increasing the financial indicators of industrial enterprises is one of the main factors of the rapid development of the capital market of our country.

In order to ensure the rapid development of the capital market in our country, we can see the introduction of an effective system of attracting investments and the capital market as one of the main sources of financing the development of the country's economy. In its formation, using the experience of developed countries, as a legal foundation, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 14, 2019 No. “Capital Market Development Agency” was established as an independent state body, and the main of its tasks is the formation, development, regulation, and legal basis of the securities market in the country, organization of corporate management in state and non-state or joint-stock companies and implementation of a unified state policy in this field was determined. Also, based on this decree, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4127 of January 24, 2019 on the establishment of the Capital Market Development Agency

of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted. This state body has set itself the task of developing the Strategy for the development of the capital market of our country for 2020-2025. Today, the low profitability of the portfolio in most enterprises and joint-stock companies, the low growth trend of their net assets, and the complexity of their requirements for operation lead to difficulties for the activities of industrial enterprises in the financial market of our country. For this reason, it is important to develop a capital market development strategy and gradually implement this strategy in order to ensure the development of enterprises' activities in the financial market and increase their financial activities.

If we talk about the prospective organizational and legal formation of enterprises, industrial enterprises and joint-stock companies occupy a leading place in the economy of today's developed countries, which is related to the long period of their development and the nature of property relations. In history, enterprises and their joint-stock form appeared at the beginning of the 18th century. Initially, it was based on cooperative enterprises, but it prevailed over them in the socialization of production and the scope of its activities.

The peak of the popularization of industrial enterprises was at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. This process mainly coincided with the period of construction and development of railway transport in developed countries. By the end of the 19th century, industrial enterprises, as joint-stock companies and companies, occupied the main leading position in the economic system of developed countries.

Joint-stock companies or companies have a number of advantages over other forms of ownership. First, the company has the ability to attract shareholders' funds

to replenish the charter fund and expand its activities, and these funds are non-refundable.

Secondly, the general management department of the company is separate from a certain management, which leads to a serious attitude towards the selection of employees who manage shareholders.

Thirdly, it will be possible to turn the entire labor team of the organization into owners by purchasing shares, which will be reflected in the results of their activities.

Fourthly, it is possible to attract suppliers and other partners to the composition of shareholders, to create a general interest in the results of economic activity.

Fifth, this form of ownership is a source of additional income for shareholders.[4]

Analysis of the financial situation of enterprises, that is, financial analysis, with the help of these broad indicators, using complex methods, is to express the availability, condition, location and level of use of financial resources of enterprises.[8]

Based on the above, it is appropriate to use a number of indicators with clear normative levels and criteria in increasing the financial activity of joint-stock companies, and in the table below we will mention the indicators related to the financial and economic activity of the enterprise.

Table of financial indicators of joint-stock companies

№	Indicator name	Calculation method	Standard level
1	Absolute liquidity coefficient	(Money + Short-term financial investments) /Short	min 0.2

2	Joriy likvidlilik koeffisiyenti	Current assets/current liabilities	min 1,25
3	Current liquidity coefficient	Equity/Debt Obligations	min 0,25
4	With their own funds security coefficient	Current assets/Sources of own funds	min 0,1
5	Equity profitability coefficient (ROE)	Net profit/Own equity	min 0,15
6	Financial independence coefficient	Own sources of funds/Balance asset	min 0.5 (optimal level 0.65-0.75)
7	Dividend income coefficient	Dividends paid/shared capital	min 0,15
8	Dividend payability coefficient	Dividends paid/net profit	1 (optimal level 0.4-0.7)
9	P/E coefficient	Market price of the share / ((net profit – dividend paid per share) / number of shares)	Optimal level 12-15
10	P/B coefficient	Market price of the share/ Balance value of the share	Optimal level 1-2

Let's look at the description and normative levels of financial indicators presented in this table one by one.[6]

Absolute liquidity coefficient (MuLK) it is the main criterion of liquidity of the joint-stock company and is found as follows:

MuLK = (Money + Short-term financial investments) / Short-term liabilities

This coefficient determines which part of the short-term liabilities will be quickly returned to the account of existing funds and fast-selling securities. The standard value will be higher than 0.2 (optimal value 0.2-0.35), such a value of absolute liquidity means that 20-35% of short-term liabilities are quickly returned by the enterprise to the account of funds.

Current liquidity ratio (JLK) indicates the adequacy of working assets to fulfill short-term liabilities and is calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{JLK = Current\ assets/current\ liabilities}$$

To what extent all working assets of the enterprise cover existing short-term debts; to what extent this debt can be covered without attracting material working capital, and finally, it allows to determine how much of the short-term debts can be covered by the most liquid value of assets, cash and short-term financial investments. The current liquidity coefficient should be at least 1.25 in the conditions of Uzbekistan.

Financial independence coefficient (MMK) indicates the share of assets covered by the company's equity capital and is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{MMK = Own\ sources\ of\ funds: Balance\ asset}$$

Usually, investors pay special attention to the value of this coefficient. In practice, the lowest limit of the standard value of the indicator is 0.5. The high coefficient means that the enterprise is in a financially stable state and independent from external creditors.

Financial leverage ratio (MLK) describes the efficiency of the enterprise's use of equity capital and is determined as follows:

$$\text{MLK} = \text{Equity/Debt Obligations}$$

The high level of this coefficient reflects the state of dependence of the enterprise on debt funds. At the moment, it affects the profitability of its funds through the effect of financial support and is used to assess the level of financial risk, that is, it determines the level of financial dependence. The level of the indicator directly depends on the composition of assets, the efficiency of their use, profitability and specialization of the enterprise.

Equity profitability coefficient (ROE) shows the share of the company's net profit in relation to its capital and is determined by the following formula:

$$\text{O'KRR (ROE)} = \text{Net profit} / \text{Equity}$$

This coefficient is considered an important financial indicator for the enterprise and shows how effectively it has used its investment in any investor, business owner, business.

Coefficient of provision of own working capital indicates the adequacy of own funds necessary to finance the current activity of the enterprise and is determined as follows:

$$\text{O'AM} = \text{Own funds/ Current assets}$$

The standard level of this indicator should be greater than 0.1. Otherwise, the financial level of the enterprise will lead to a decrease among current assets.

Dividend Income Coefficient (DDK) – shows the amount of dividend per share and is calculated as follows:

DDK = Dividends paid/shared capital

A high coefficient is considered a positive situation. If the dividend income coefficient is less than 0.15 (15%), it indicates that the joint-stock company is not able to effectively place its assets on the stock market. As a result, there may be dissatisfaction among investors. Otherwise, above 0.15 (15%) indicates that the market price of the shares is increasing.

Dividend Payability Coefficient (DTQK) – is a share of the profit paid to shareholders in the form of dividends and is calculated as follows:

DTQK = Dividends paid/net profit

This indicator provides information on how much of the company's funds will be paid to shareholders in order to accumulate money reserves or repay its debts, reinvest them for economic development. Also, this coefficient shows the level of maturity of the company.

It is presented in the table P/E coefficient - this is a financial indicator equal to the ratio of the market price of shares of joint-stock companies to their annual income in one share and is found as follows:

$$P/E = \frac{P}{EPS}$$

Here P – stock market price,

$$EPS = \frac{\text{net profit} - \text{dividend paid per share}}{\text{number of shares}}$$

This indicator is one of the main indicators used to assess the investment attractiveness of the joint-stock company. The small value of the coefficient shows that the profit of the company is valued cheaper than the profit of another company with a higher coefficient in the market. The optimal level of the coefficient should be in the range of 12-15.

It is presented in the table P/B coefficient – is determined by the ratio of the market price of shares of joint-stock companies to the balance sheet value in one share using the following formula:

$$P/B = \frac{\text{market value of the share}}{\text{balance sheet value of the share}}$$

This indicator shows that the shares of joint-stock companies are related to the market value and balance sheet value, as well as the liquidity and attractiveness of the shares of the joint-stock company. Its optimal level should be in the range of 1-2.

Thus, with the help of the financial indicators of joint-stock companies, the problem of increasing its financial activity and the effectiveness of its use remains more urgent today than ever. Therefore, the relevance, scientific and practical importance of this problem in modern economic conditions and the insufficient level of the methodology of the analysis of the formation of the enterprise's capital. Also, the capital of enterprises or joint-stock companies is one of the main economic categories, the essence of which has been determined by scientific opinion for several centuries. In this thesis, capital was considered at the micro level, that is, as the capital of enterprises or as the capital of a joint-stock company. It is in this organizational and legal form that the features of capital formation, management and efficiency of

its use appear. The capital of the enterprise is the main factor of production or service. At the same time, it also describes the main financial resources that generate income. Also, the capital of the enterprise ensures the financial well-being of its owners and serves as the main source of financial resources for it.

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